

FE-DIC FOR IDENTIFICATION PURPOSES

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SUMMARY

An Integrated Digital Image Correlation (I-DIC) scheme is proposed to identify mechanical properties of composite materials. Two ingredients, namely, Finite Element based Digital Image Correlation and Finite Element Model Updating, are interleaved. Finite element simulations are used to build a small basis of displacement fields, itself considered in the DIC analysis where the corresponding amplitudes are the material properties to be identified. This coupling allows one to decrease noise sensitivity even in the case of very small element sizes. Biaxial tests performed on planar cruciform specimens are used to show the applicability of the proposed method.

Keywords: Digital Image Correlation, Finite Element, Updating method, Identification, Biaxial tests

INTRODUCTION

Among full field measurement techniques [1], white light correlation based methods are emerging because of their versatility and simplicity of use. Most of the used techniques for performing Digital Image Correlation (DIC) are based on local matching procedures [2-4]. They give access to dense displacement fields at distinct scales mostly in two dimensions. Extensions to three dimensional displacement fields on a surface is achieved through stereo-correlation at the macro or structural scale by using pairs of optical images. The approach has more recently been extended to volumetric data [5-9]. DIC represents an attractive tool to study and monitor the behaviour of composite materials and structures. It is becoming one of the major counterparts for finite element simulations and makes possible their “strong” coupling to identify and / or validate constitutive parameters [10-11].

Many identification methods have already been proposed [12]. Finite Element Model Updating [13], or FEMU, is a very common and widespread technique. This kind of approach may lead to practical difficulties for at least two reasons. On the one hand, as highlighted earlier, full field measurements are usually based on signal processing tools. They do not account for any *a priori* knowledge about the behaviour of the observed material. On the other hand, the actual boundary conditions generally differ from their modelling. A solution is to use experimental measurements as boundary conditions for the simulation. However, these data are noisy and may cause artificial discrepancies in the identification procedure. This remark is particularly relevant when one tries to

identify elastic parameters of composite materials. It is therefore proposed to develop an Integrated Digital Image Correlation (I-DIC) technique, FEMU-inspired, that gives access not only to a displacement field, but directly to mechanical parameters.

It is proposed herein to compare the results of the identification given by the I-DIC procedure with those obtained with a classical two-step approach. A biaxial test performed on an SMC composite is considered. One focuses on the identification of in-plane Poisson's ratio. First, the principle of the implemented FE-DIC technique is briefly described. Second, a particular version of FEMU is presented and applied to FE-DIC measurements. Last, the new coupled DIC-FEMU procedure, designed to minimize the impact of a small signal to noise ratio, is evaluated. The influence of the mesh size on the identified values is discussed.

FE-DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

Let us consider two grey level images f and g (f being the reference picture, and g the deformed one) taken at two distinct stages of loading. Contrary to *local* approaches [2-4], the DIC method used herein is based on the Brightness Conservation (BC) assumption [14] written on a *global* level. The BC hypothesis means that the image texture is passively advected by a displacement field u . The problem consists in *identifying* the best displacement field u by minimizing the correlation residual functional, Φ

$$\Phi(u) = \int_{\Omega} [g(x) - f(x + u(x))]^2 dx \quad (1)$$

One takes advantage of meaningful (*i.e.*, mechanical) bases to decompose the sought displacement field. The chosen DIC formulation [15] is such that any displacement basis is easily incorporated into the formulation

$$u(x) = \sum_n a_n \psi_n(x) = [\psi(x)]\{u\} \quad (2)$$

where ψ_n are the vector shape functions, and a_n their associated degrees of freedom. In a matrix-vector format, $[\psi]$ is a row vector containing the values of the shape functions ψ_n and $\{u\}$ the column vector of the degrees of freedom a_n . At this level of generality, one may choose to decompose the displacement field $u(x)$ on a more or less "mechanically rich" basis. One may for example use classical FE discretizations. In that case, the DIC problem consists in looking for the nodal displacements minimizing a weak form of the BC functional Φ . It is proposed to solve this minimization problem through successive linearizations of Φ

$$\Phi_{lin}(u) = \int_{\Omega} [f(x) + [\psi(x)]\{u\} \cdot \nabla f(x) - g(x)]^2 d\underline{x} \quad (3)$$

One obtains classical linear systems $[M]\{a\} = \{b\}$ to solve, where $\{a\}$ is the vector of unknown nodal displacements. $[M]$ and the right hand side $\{b\}$ are respectively a matrix and a vector determined using the images and the shape functions. The same formulation is used in 3D cases [9,16], where the challenge consists in performing time efficient computations, and also in dealing with a considerable amount of data. A *multiscale* approach allows for dealing with large displacements.

In the convenient framework of the in-house developed “LMT platform,” one simply selects the type of elements used, and the associated interpolation schemes are automatically generated [17].

TWO-STEP FEMU-BASED IDENTIFICATION PROCEDURE

The measured displacement fields are now used as input data for an identification procedure. FEMU [13] is a convenient way to identify mechanical properties, starting only from a picture sequence. It consists in updating iteratively the material properties in a Finite Element simulation to reduce the difference between measured and simulated displacement fields (it is now perfectly relevant since *the same kinematic description is used*). The displacement fields measured on the non free nodes of the mesh boundary are chosen as Dirichlet conditions for mechanical simulations (to avoid errors linked to an erroneous modelling of the grip/specimen load transfer). The elastic problem illustrated in Figure 1 is chosen as an example. A first snapshot of a Region Of Interest (ROI) is taken before loading, and a second picture is captured during loading. Digital Image Correlation allows one to measure the displacement field of the specimen.

Figure 1. Classical FEMU approach. Displacements are obtained on a mesh that is subsequently used for comparison with FE simulations.

Simulations are run with varying parameter sets, until DIC and numerical displacements match at best. It is worth recalling that “low contrast” areas lead to high noise sensitivity, and should carry a smaller weight than “high contrasted” ones. It can be proven that the best scalar product to quantify the match between DIC and computed nodal displacements is

$$\langle a, b \rangle_M = \langle a, Mb \rangle \quad (4)$$

where M is the assembled DIC matrix, which is symmetric and positive by construction. In the case of fully differentiable energies, one may compute the derivatives of the simulated nodal displacement vector, u_s , with respect to each material parameter, p_i . Let u_d denote the nodal displacement vector obtained from DIC. The following functional,

$$\tau(p_i) = \|u_s(p_i) - u_d\|_M \quad (5)$$

is to be minimized. This is achieved iteratively through successive linearizations

$$M\left(\sum_i \frac{\partial u_s}{\partial p_i} (p_i^{n+1} - p_i^n) + u_s(p_i^n) - u_d\right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

Biaxial experiments carried out on planar cruciform specimens made of composite materials are then used to evaluate this method. The Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC) material, made of short glass fibres and an epoxy resin, is assumed to be initially homogeneous and isotropic. The biaxial specimen is thin enough (5 mm) with respect to the size of the ROI (> 60 mm) to consider a plane stress state. Pictures taken at various stages of the loading are exploited. Distinct mesh sizes are used. Their impact on estimated Poisson's ratio with the I-DIC procedure is investigated.

In that case only Poisson's ratio was searched for using data shown in Figure 2. Only one minimum is found. One has to emphasize that material properties identification may become far more complex. Strong non-linearities may lead to several local minima and a degradation of the convergence rate. For illustrative examples and solutions, one may refer to Ref. [18]. In all cases, this two-step procedure leads to a trade-off to manage image noise. Using the two-stage procedure (pure correlation and subsequent mechanical analysis), the noise sensitivity becomes dominant for small element sizes (Figure 3) yielding solutions, *if it converges*, that might correspond to local minima. Unfortunately, small elements are mandatory when dealing with "complex" geometries, e.g., with small corner radii (as those in Figure 2) or small angles, which are not uncommon. However, as one can do with any Finite Element representation, it is possible to use meshes refined only around "complex" borders. For those elements, the noise sensitivity problem remains prominent. Figure 3 illustrates this point.

Figure 2. Example of measured (left) and computed (right) displacement fields. The distance, defined in Equation (4), between these fields was minimized with respect to elastic parameters.

Figure 3. Fitted Poisson's ratio vs. mesh size (in pixels). Coarse meshes lead to poor kinematic representations whereas fine meshes lead to high noise sensitivity.

INTEGRATED DIC METHOD

The approach presented in this section originates from the idea that, at the end of the identification step, the internal displacements are not needed, namely, they are only intermediate data, within a global procedure whose final goal is to find material properties. For mechanical simulations, one needs *at least* the Dirichlet boundary conditions (displacements) on non free borders. Thus, it is possible to condense the correlation problem so that the remaining unknowns are only the displacements on the non free borders, which have smooth variations and do not need fine representations, and the material properties. For the experiment shown in Figure 2, one may for example use meshes like that of Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of a mesh used for the coupled DIC-FEMU procedure. The element size is a decreasing function of $\partial u_s / \partial p_i$.

An Integrated DIC procedure is then followed. Advantage is taken of the freedom of using *any displacement basis* in the global DIC approach. Instead of utilising a standard FE description, one can build the basis directly from the FE *mechanical* modelling. The idea is to use in the DIC procedure a FE displacement field computed using the known boundary conditions and some initial values of the mechanical parameters. A FEMU-like technique allows then to tune the mechanical parameters to minimize the BC functional by using a displacement basis constructed as the result of small variations of

the sought mechanical parameters. In that case, the displacement basis has a strong mechanical content. A “rough” DIC measurement is then first performed to get the experimental boundary conditions that are applied on the edges of the region of interest (ROI). It is proposed to use larger elements on the edges of the ROI to decrease the measurement uncertainties (Figure 1).

Figure 5. Poisson’s ratio versus element size (in pixels) around the free borders (elements on the non free border are of constant sizes) as obtained from the coupled DIC-FEMU procedure (+). The • symbols show the same quantity obtained with a uniform element size using the two-step FEMU based procedure.

Figure 5 shows the change of Poisson’s ratio ν versus the element size on high p_i sensitive zones. The non free borders are meshed with elements coarse enough to minimize the noise sensitivity. The stability of ν -estimates is quite spectacular as compared to the previous approach. Within the explored range of element size, $\nu = 0.308 \pm 0.003$.

CONCLUSION

A specific global Finite-Element Digital Image Correlation procedure was proposed. It allows one to express the measured displacement field with the same description as that used for numerical computations and to minimize the number of unknown kinematic variables for a better accuracy. The identification of constitutive parameters based on FE-DIC measurements by using a Finite Element Updating Method was presented. The latter technique makes use of a specific scalar product resulting from DIC that minimizes the sensitivity to noise. The identification of Poisson’s ratio of a composite material was presented as an illustration of the procedure.

Furthermore, the flexibility of the finite element representation offers a way to couple strongly DIC and FEMU for enhanced accuracy and robustness of the identification. However, the presentation of the methodology has been kept as general as possible to encompass within the same formalism non-linear constitutive laws.

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